

EdiCitNet News Template

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

EdiCitNet News

Dear all,

Please share the information related to your news using this template. We will use this information to produce news on the Website.

Don't forget to share at least one picture, to make the news more inviting.

News Information

* **News Title:** Please enter here a news title (Example: City Team Meeting in Berlin; EdiCitNet Workshop in Oslo, etc.)

Feel free to be creative !!!

Text of 30 to 150 characters will be accepted

The toolbox is already prepared to gather information on Edible City Solutions

* **Description:** Please enter here the text related to the news you are sharing. It can be a local event, meeting or other, related to Edible City Solutions (ECS) and/or EdiCitNet in your cities.

Text of 500 to 2500 characters will be accepted

The first Thursday of February took place a WP2 meeting with great news. WP2 announced that the toolbox is ready to collect information on Edible City Solutions. The main functionalities of the toolbox are already working and EdiCitNet partners can use it to map the Edible City Solutions in their cities. As well as for Edible City Solutions of the rest of the world.

Once a profile for an Edible City Solution is created, it appears on the Edible Map and toolbox users can visualize its public profile and receive comments from other users. The users can search Edible City Solutions using basic and advanced filters to find relevant information for their needs. Then, through the Edible List, that information can be downloaded in an excel file for further analysis. Furthermore, Edible City Solutions can get a concise assessment in terms of sustainability, urban challenges and ecosystem services based on the data they provided.

In the same meeting, WP2 discussed with cities the best strategies to collect data from the Edible City Solutions in order to be as efficient as possible.

Feature Image: Please send an image that will be displayed together with the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

5ace6569-3353-4f40-9b45-c07d60e202aa/Captura_de_pantalla_2021-02-22_104223.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

3a8292e8-04af-4765-8fbc-491d7cdb8ea2/Captura_de_pantalla_2021-02-22_104935.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

9f045e37-5be2-4c8d-966d-0205379ddc32/Captura_de_pantalla_2021-02-22_105036.png

Additional Image (Optional): You can share here an additional image that will be displayed in the news.

The maximum file size is 1 MB

Only files of the type png,jpg,jpeg,gif,bmp are allowed

527ca6a7-b36c-4ba2-a949-8b6d462decfc/Captura_de_pantalla_2021-02-22_105142.png

Hereby I confirm we have the rights to share this picture in EdiCitNet news.

URL: Here you can share an URL related to the news like a link to a video, website, etc.

<https://toolbox.edicitnet.com/>

Date: Please confirm the date of the news you are sharing.

04/02/2021

Please specify a location related to the news you are sharing. (City, Address, Venue, etc.)

500 character(s) maximum

Girona, Spain

Contact Person

* **First and last Name:** Please enter your complete name. It will be displayed as author of the news.

Josep Pueyo-Ros

* **Organisation:** Please enter the name of your organisation.

ICRA

* **Position:** Please indicate your position in your organisation.

Postdoc researcher

* **City & Country:** Please indicate the city and country where you are contacting us from.

Girona, Spain

* **Email:** Your email will not be shown in the news, unless you explicitly indicate it below. We will use it to contact you if we have any question.

jpueyo@icra.cat

I want my Email to be displayed in the news.

- Yes
 No

Social Media

* I agree to share my news on the EdiCitNet Twitter and/or Instagram

- Yes, both of them
 No, none of them
 Only on Twitter
 Only on Instagram

Additional Comments:

500 character(s) maximum

Contact

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